

EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING FOSTERS EMPLOYEE GREEN BEHAVIOUR: A SEQUENTIAL MODERATED MEDIATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This study makes a unique contribution to the transformation journey toward sustainability by empirically studying the moderating function of employee engagement and organizational commitment with self-esteem in the relationship between employee well-being and employee green behaviors. Researchers in organizational behavior have been examining aspects that impact employee green behaviour. However, few studies have examined positive benefits of employee well-being on employee green behaviour. Purpose of this study is to look at linkages between employee well-being, employee green behavior, self-esteem, organizational commitment, and employee engagement. Surveys are conducted with 285 employees from higher education institution and universities of Pakistan. PLS-SEM approach is applied to evaluate the connection between variables. Employee well-being also has a strong beneficial influence on self-esteem and employee green behavior. Finally, organizational commitment and employee engagement initiatives favorably moderated the association between employee well-being, self-esteem and employee green behaviour.

Keywords: Employee Well-being (EWB), Employee green behavior (EGB), Self-esteem, Organizational commitment (OC) and Employee engagement (EE).

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between EWB and EGB has emerged as significant study issue (Gyensare et al., 2024). EGB is considered as positive activity that addresses attitudes and enhancement of the green behavior of employees for organizational outcomes (Vanisri & Chandrapadhy, 2024). Sadiq (2023) described EGB as a collection of workplace behaviors taken by workers to preserve environment and support organization's long-term success, such as resource conservation, waste management, environmental protection knowledge acquisition, and sustainable labor. EGB

successfully increases organizational productivity while also providing employees with a greater sense of social benefit (Katz et al., 2022). Green behavior has been popular with businesses and individuals seeking to help both the organization and the environment (Unsworth et al., 2021). Ercantan and Eyupoglu (2022) contended that demand of internal organizational environment forces businesses to implement green behaviors in as many particular work processes as feasible inside the firm. Many studies have examined the elements that influence the facilitation and development of

EGB, but few have investigated how it impacts employees (Zacher et al., 2023).

Individually, green behavior meets needs of work tasks or environmental protection objectives, but it also helps employees earn task incentives, increase job satisfaction, and improve professional, physical, and emotional health (Tang et al., 2023). Individuals and organizations both aim for well-being and people who have a higher sense of well-being are more driven at work and contribute more to productivity (Sonnetag et al., 2023). Employees become more focused on well-being, when their basic needs are fulfilled (Kaufman, 2023). According to Pradhan and Hati (2022), employee well-being includes employee's awareness, job satisfaction but also passionate and psychosomatic experience and happiness expressed during and after work. Engaging in green activity can boost employees' perception of efficacy and relevance, leading to improved well-being (Martínez-Falcó et al., 2024). Previous study has discovered that when employees recognize the rewards of their work, people generate optimistic and personal decisions about significance, talent, quality, and forte, known as self-esteem, therefore meeting inner necessities (Abbas et al., 2024). As a result, self-esteem is a key indication of well-being and may influence link between EGB and EWB (Saleem et al., 2024). When people assess their own conduct, they are impacted by their colleagues or employers, and organizational support can boost employee well-being. Organizational commitment and employee engagement activities increase self-esteem, which increases employee green behavior (Hur et al., 2022). Employees that have a strong organizational commitment and participate in environmental activities understand the benefits of green behavior and are more likely having higher self-esteem and EWB (Cheng et al., 2022), paid the growing emphasis on environmental issues, greater attention should be paid to how green workplace practices might boost employee well-being. This study looks at association among EWB and EGB, especially how and when EWB influences EGB. This study offers dimensional research, outcome factors of EGB, allowing organizations and workers to clearly perceive beneficial benefits of green behavior on those who engage in it. The research findings assist

managers better understand EGB by providing theoretical guidance for increasing EWB and improving EGB.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Self Esteem and Employee Well Being

Employees' well-being increases when their self-esteem grows, that is reliable with self-determination theory, critical theory underpinning for well-being research (Nunes et al., 2024). DeYoung and Tiberius (2023) researched that Individuals are viewed as inherently active creatures; as a result, achieving internal desires is more important for well-being than addressing external needs such as material possessions and money. Employees with strong self-esteem think their jobs are meaningful and capable of attaining certain goals (Wicaksono & Ratnawati, 2022). Employees are given the freedom to perform tasks and choose their own work style; additionally, employees believe they have a significant effect on organizational issues; all of these physical perspectives indicate that workers' fundamental inner needs have been met. Employees with low self-esteem perceive their job as worthless, have little confidence in their own talents, have limited autonomy in accomplishing work tasks, and are unable to have a substantial effect on corporate strategy or decision-making (Laaser & Bolton, 2022). Qin and Men (2023) discovered that in these conditions, employees' key inner needs are not addressed, resulting in a reduced degree of well-being. When considered together, following hypothesis may be proposed:

Hypothesis 1: EWB is positively related to Self-esteem.

2.2 Employee Well-being and Employee Green Behaviour

Climate change and environmental degradation have a global impact on economic growth, lifestyles, and health, so our capacity to reduce CO₂ emissions and environmental degradation impacts societal well-being (Aladejare, 2023). "Well-being" refers to the psychological emotions felt when pursuing happiness and avoiding sorrow (Park et al., 2023). Mendonça et al. (2022) defined EWB as an employee's positive mental health status in workplace, indicating their individual physiological arousal state, psychological satisfaction level at work, and it is

used to measure mental health of organizational employees. According to study (Nasir & Irfan, 2023), personal experiences such as moral values, employee well-being, self-esteem, and employee engagement may all have a positive influence on employee green behavior. Employee well-being can improve an individual's subjective green behavior by raising self-esteem and organizational commitment (Edosomwan et al., 2023). Pro-social conduct encompasses any behaviors that match social norms while also benefiting people, organizations and society (Toumbourou, 2016); green behavior is one that benefits both companies and the environment. Employees who are careless about green development and squander resources may suffer reprimands from both supervisors and coworkers, causing a loss of faith in the organization's growth and sustainability (Afzal & Siddiqui, 2021). This can lead to less good psychological and emotional experiences, lower EWB, and negative feelings. EGB can drive people to engage in pro-environmental and pro-organizational activities, resulting in improved well-being despite workplace limits and expectations (Zhang et al., 2021). To conclude, following hypothesis is proposed:

Thus, Hypothesis H_2 proposes that employee well-being is positively related to employee green behavior.

2.3 Self-Esteem and Employee Green Behaviour

Self-esteem is a consistent individual characteristic attribute (De Moor et al., 2021). Employees having high self-esteem are more confident in dealing with failure, can cope with unexpected changes, believe in their own talents, and are flexible (Zhang et al., 2021). Self-esteem improves ability of dealing stress and exhaustion. Previous research has indicated that self-esteem can act as a mediator between other qualities (Pandey et al., 2021). Self-esteem promotes positive and negative sentiments (Shimizu et al., 2023). To avoid biased responses, "positive" and "negative" items were presented successively, when responding to the items; readers may have confused sentiments about whether they represent an optimistic or pessimistic viewpoint (Szuster et al., 2022). When assessing self-esteem, many researchers take a dichotomous approach (Valkenburg et al.,

2021); the dichotomous method divides self-esteem into two categories: high and poor. Barnard and Curry (2011) define strong self-esteem as feeling appreciated, whereas poor self-esteem results in sentiments of self-contempt and self-pity. Hur et al. (2022) discovered that employee green behavior that benefits the firm is an important influence in one's self-esteem. Volunteering to help others can boost self-esteem and earn respect (Hollas et al., 2022). Consistent volunteering boosts self-awareness and self-esteem (Jo et al., 2021). According to Zhang et al. (2021), employees having higher self-esteem think their job is more relevant and achievable, and self-esteem satisfies people's basic internal requirements. Self-esteem allows people to control their behavior and fulfill their roles in organizations (Kim & Beehr, 2022). According to self-determination theory, stronger self-esteem correlates with better employee well-being (Nunes et al., 2024). Gardner (2020) noted that people with low self-esteem may lack confidence, autonomy, and a sense of meaninglessness in their employment, resulting in unmet demands.

Hypothesis 3: self-esteem is significantly associated with Employee Green Behaviour.

2.4 Mediation Impact of Self-esteem

Employees with strong self-esteem think that their job is significant and that they can handle specific tasks (Mihaela et al., 2022). Employees are given the freedom to perform tasks and choose their own work style (Tingo & Mseti, 2022). Furthermore, employees believe they have a big influence on corporate strategy and management (Tingo & Mseti, 2022). These psychological perspectives all suggest that workers' fundamental inner needs have been met (Messmann & Kreijns, 2022). According to self-determination theory, EWB will evolve accordingly (Vijaikis & Poškus, 2024). Employees with low self-esteem may see their work as meaningless, lack confidence in capabilities, have limited sovereignty in carrying out duties, and have minimal impact on business strategy or decision-making (Bertrandias et al., 2021). Employees' basic inner needs are not met in this circumstance, leading to a diminished feeling of well-being (Breaugh, 2021). Many researchers use a binary method to measuring self-esteem (Pignault et al., 2023).

Aikpitanyi et al. (2022) define good self-esteem as feeling appreciated, whereas low self-esteem causes sentiments of self-contempt and self-pity. Volunteering to assist others can boost self-esteem and earn respect (Hollas et al., 2022). According to Zhang et al. (2021), employees with higher self-esteem think their job is more relevant and achievable. Self-esteem addresses a person's basic inner requirements. Self-esteem helps individuals regulate their behavior and fulfill their roles in organizations (Gómez-Jorge & Díaz-Garrido, 2024). According to self-determination theory, stronger self-esteem correlates with better employee well-being (Wang et al., 2022). Employees with poor self-esteem may lack self-reliance, autonomy, and sense of meaninglessness in their employment, leading in unmet demands (Gori et al., 2023). According to the Social Identity Theory, employees who participate in green behavior may experience an improvement in self-esteem (Darvishmotevali & Altinay, 2022), which improves their overall well-being. As a result, we propose the following hypotheses.

Hypothesis 4: self-esteem mediates the relationship between Employee well-being and Employee Green Behaviour.

2.5 Organizational Commitment and Employee Engagement as a Moderator

Organizational commitment fosters employee attitudes and behavior by displaying care for their needs, offering support, and acknowledging the importance of their job (Al-Refaei et al., 2023). Employees personalize organization and may challenge its goals, demonstrating that people have different opinions on organizational commitment (Sumardjo & Supriadi, 2023). Organizational

commitment can help people satisfy their communal and emotive requirements, such as admiration, esteem, wisdom of belonging, and emotional support (Afolashade et al., 2024). Sujatha et al. (2023) concluded that Organizational commitment being a moderator enhances the impact of employee well-being on Self-esteem, so due to organizational commitment self-esteem having low or medium effect will turn into high achievements. When workers see a higher degree of corporate commitment, they will grasp the benefits of implementing employee green behavior and will find it easier to fulfill their social and psychological requirements, leading in enhanced self-esteem (Zhang et al., 2021).

Hypothesis 5: Organizational commitment positively moderates relationship between Employee well-being and self-esteem in strengthening Employee Green Behaviour.

Similarly, employee engagement and involvement also influences the conditions that impacts and moderates the condition which self-esteem directly impacts on employee green behaviour (Hur et al., 2022). When adding employee engagement between self-esteem and employee green behaviour, it eventually enhances the employee green behaviour in positive way (Khan et al., 2022). As self-esteem also positively impacts on employee green behaviour but when employee engages keenly in work, then the behaviour of employees about work reflects with positivity which is the symbol of the achievement of employee positive green behaviour (Elbers et al., 2023). So, the hypothesis can be elaborated as:

Hypothesis 6: Employee engagement moderates link between self-esteem and Employee Green Behaviour.

The Figure 1 illustrates the hypothesized Model

3 RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Data Collection

Data were gathered via questionnaires distributed to full-time, regular faculty members in Pakistani different universities and higher education institutions, with a response rate of approximately 58.83%. Probability sampling technique, simple random sampling methodology has been adopted.

3.2 Measurement

Self-esteem was measured using Rosenberg ten-item scale Rosenberg (1965), such as “I feel that I am a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.” Cronbach alpha coefficient was 0.938. Employee well-being (EWB): measures were adopted from Zheng et al. (2015), 18-item scale. EGB is measured by 13 items scale developed by Graves et al. (2013). Measurement of organizational commitment variable consists of eight questions adopted from De Waal (2018). The employee engagement variable consists of eleven questions adopted from Saks (2019). Data is collected from full-time, regular faculty members at educational institutions. Respondents completed an online questionnaire in Google Docs. A simple random sampling is a probabilistic approach of collecting data from consenting participants in research investigations. 285 structured questionnaires were distributed to respondents during February

and March 2025 and collected their responses. Out of 285 responses, 20 were removed due to inadequate answers during data cleaning, leaving 265 authorized.

3.3 Statistical Analysis

This study used a PLS-SEM technique to assess the link between variables and latent constructs, which was reproduced by inner model, relationship indicators, and latent variables (Kura 2016). PLS-SEM is applied to evaluate indirect effects for route coefficients using bootstrapping techniques. The model given in tables 1 and 2 was examined for reliability, consistency, convergent validity, and discriminatory validity (Hair et al. 2013). Internal consistency reliability was assessed using composite reliability, with each latent construct having a coefficient greater than 0.70. Table 1 demonstrates composite reliability ranging from 0.912 to 0.734, internal consistency reliability exceeding 0.70, and average variance extracted AVE for latent components more than 0.50 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Hair et al 2013). Table below shows that each latent construct exceeds the requirement of 0.50. Alpha value was used to assess internal consistency and all constructs had values over 0.8, suggesting excellent dependability.

Table 1

Validity and Composite Reliability of Study Variables

	Items	Alpha Value	CR	AVE	MSV
Employee Well Being	18	0.887	0.861	0.683	0.431
Self-esteem	10	0.867	0.912	0.535	0.587
Employee Green Behaviour	13	0.935	0.795	0.586	0.446
Organizational Commitment	08	0.844	0.734	0.645	0.377
Employee Engagement	11	0.812	0.851	0.574	0.496

CR =Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted, and MSV = Maximum Shared Variance

Table 2 shows descriptive and inferential statistics for the study variables. The central tendency of the variables was determined using mean values and standard deviation for the distribution. The mean values were neither low

nor high, with the exception of Employee Green Behaviour (6.99), which showed that respondents reported high levels of Employee Green Behaviour. Moreover, standard deviation was also normal and did not signify much dispersion in dataset.

Table 2

Correlation matrix between studied variables

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Employee Well Being	3.89.	0.98	1				
Self-esteem	6.86	1.87	0.12**	1			
Employee Green Behaviour	6.99	0.91	0.08**	0.16**	1		
Organizational Commitment	5.99	0.89	0.13**	0.645	-0.08	1	
Employee Engagement	6.34	1.02	0.03	0.574	0.49*	0.05	1

SD = Standard Deviation

Correlation values were also in supposed direction for all variables. Employee Well-being was shown to have substantial optimistic link with Employee Green Behaviour (0.08, $p < 0.05$), as well as Employee Engagement (0.01, $p < 0.05$) and Organizational Commitment (0.13, $p < 0.05$). However, the connection between Employee Well-Being and Self-esteem (0.12, $p > 0.05$) and Employee Green Behaviour (0.12,

$p > 0.05$) was favorable but not statistically significant. Additionally, Employee well-being was positively and statistically related to Organizational Commitment (0.13, $p < 0.05$) and Employee Engagement (0.03, $p < 0.05$). Also found a positive and significant correlation between Self-esteem and Employee Green Behaviour (0.16, $p < 0.01$).

Table 3

Summary of Direct and Mediation effects

Variable	Estimates	Remarks
EWB → SE	0.17**	Supported
EWB → EGB	0.18**	Supported
SE → EGB	0.19**	Supported
EWB → SE → EGB	0.13**	Supported

Notes: EWB=Employee Well-being, SE=Self-esteem, EGB= Employee Green Behaviour, and denotes ** $p < 0.01$.

Table 3 summarizes our expected structural equation modelling findings. Research shows that employee well-being has a significant positive influence on self-esteem (0.17, $p < 0.01$). As a consequence, employee well-being increases by one unit, and their self-esteem increases by 0.17 units, assuming no other changes. This data supports Hypothesis 1, which states that there is a positive association between employee well-being and self-esteem. The results consequently support Hypothesis 1. Similarly, the EWB has positive and significant impact on EGB (0.18, $p < 0.01$). So EWB increases by one unit by increasing EGB by 0.18 units, which concludes the positive connection between EWB and

EGB, hence, Hypothesis 2 is supported. Self-esteem significantly improved employee green behaviour (0.19, $p < 0.01$). As a result, for every one unit increase in self-esteem, employee green behaviour increases by 0.19 units. This finding supports Hypothesis 3 findings of a positive association between self-esteem and employee green behaviour. The facts consequently support Hypothesis 3. In current study, self-esteem association 0.13 was shown to be a significant and positive mediator of EWB and EGB. In addition, study calculated overall effect of EWB on EGB. 0.32 ($SL \rightarrow GC + SL \rightarrow GKS \rightarrow GC = 0.19 + 0.13 = 0.32$). Thus, SE explains for 41% of the mediation effect ($0.13/0.32 = 0.41$). Hypothesis 4 stated that SE would be mediated as an indirect outcome of EWB on EGB. Therefore, Hypothesis 4 is accepted.

Table 4
Summary of Moderation Effects

	Coefficient	Sig.	BC 95% CI	
			Lower	Upper
EWB*OC → SE	0.27*	0.00	0.12	0.51
SE*EE → EGB	0.29*	0.00	0.10	0.49

Sig = Significance, CI = Confidence Interval, EWB = Employee Well-being, OC = Organizational Commitment, EGB = Employee Green Behaviour, EE= Employee Engagement, SE= Self-esteem, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01

Moderating effects of OC on the direct effect of EWB and SE are listed in Table 4. Additionally, a moderation effect of EE on the direct effect of SE on the EGB is observed. It is stated in Hypothesis 5 that OC strengthens the connection between EWB and SE. Therefore, the collaboration effect of EWB and OC on SE was determined to be positive and statistically significant at 0.28 (95% CI [0.12, 0.51]) based on the examining moderation influence. Table 4 indicates that EWB had a direct impact of 0.17 on SE. Therefore, the moderation effect of OC added 0.11 units to this. As a result, Hypothesis 5 can be trusted. The moderating effect of EE on the direct effect of SE and EGB was investigated in a similar manner. It was stated in Hypothesis 6 that EE strengthens the connection between SE and the EGB. Therefore, the collaboration impact of SE and EE on EGB was found to be positive and statistically significant at 0.29 (95% CI [0.10, 0.49]) for the evaluation of the moderation effect. Additionally, it was mentioned in Table 4 that SE has a 0.19 direct impact on EGB. As a result, the scenario as a whole is strengthened by 0.10 units due to the moderation effect of EE. As a result, Hypothesis 6 is supported.

4 DISCUSSION

Goal of this study was to determine impact of employee well-being on EGB at higher education institutions and universities. Previous research on EGB concentrated on individual practice, influencing others, and firm perception (Vansri & Chandrapadhy 2024; Zibarras & Coan 2015). Previous study investigated EGB through task and voluntary employee behavior (Aboramadan 2022; Saleem et al., 2020). Organizational commitment and employee engagement were shown to moderate association between green activities and well-being. Self-

esteem has a role of mediator between EWB and employee well-

being. This study developed a hypothetical model of "green behavior, self-esteem, and well-being" to investigate if self-esteem serves as a mediating variable. Although there is no substantial direct association between EGB and, other studies (Zhang et al., 2021) have shown a significant relationship. Previous study has found an association between self-esteem and employee well-being (Mäkikangas & Kinnunen, 2003; Satuf et al., 2018).

Adopting green behavior does not always imply compromising employee well-being. Despite this, employees Green behavior in the workplace involves decreasing waste, reusing resources, and recycling obsolete products. According to Ahmed et al. (2020), employees with higher levels of well-being perform work confidently, have less job fatigue are likely to recommend ecologically responsible solutions to the organization. Kim and Beehr (2022) and Zhang et al. (2021) discovered that EGB had linked to better self-esteem levels. Identifying and selecting green habits is critical for employees to successfully execute them. This study found a substantial indirect relationship between EGB and EWB, with self-esteem serving as a completely mediating factor. Employees with higher self-esteem have better well-being, which supports the self-determination idea at the heart of well-being research. This study adds to previous research (Zhang et al., 2021), which found that green activities among employees are a strong predictor of workplace well-being. The study discovered a favorable link between employee green activities and well-being, with self-esteem serving as a mediator. However, there was no discernible link among employee green behavior and workplace green behaviour. Current study provides theoretical guidelines for firms seeking to encourage environmentally

friendly conduct and develop EWB. Research which using self-determination theory revealed that high self-esteem effectively transfers optimistic effects of EGB to EWB.

Previous assessments of EGB focused on specific practice, manipulating others, and organizational opinions (Zacher et al., 2023). Identifying and selecting green behavior is crucial for spreading it among employees (Feng et al., 2024). Green behavior prepares individuals to scientifically execute green behavior (Gelino et al., 2021). This study investigated the components that influence EGB outcomes, created a theoretical model of EGB, self-esteem, EWB, explored organizational commitment and employee engagement initiatives changed overall model. The investigation discovered a positive link between EGB and EWB, which validates the theory developed in this study. Previous research (Zhang et al., 2021) demonstrated an optimistic relationship between self-esteem and EWB. Furthermore, self-esteem may moderate relationship among EGB and EWB. Organizational commitment and employee engagement play a moderating role in the positive relationship between EWB, EGB, and self-esteem; that is, high organizational commitment amplifies the positive influence of EWB on self-esteem, while high employee engagement strengthens the influence of self-esteem on EGB. Organizational commitment efforts increase the link between EWB and EGB by boosting self-esteem. Greater organizational commitment efforts are associated with higher self-esteem levels. Similarly, employee engagement businesses foster the link between EWB and EGB via self-esteem. Findings provide suggestions for businesses seeking to boost employee well-being and improve EWB.

4.1 Theoretical Implications

Empirical investigation indicates that EWB can effectively promote EGB. Employee well-being refers to employees' subjective contentment with their lives, job, and psyche (Pradhan & Hati, 2022). Employees with higher well-being perform better at work, feel less burnout, and are more likely to suggest environmentally responsible ideas to the organization (Ferrara et al., 2022). As a result, it significantly affects the company's survival and long-term development

(Farida & Setiawan, 2022). Implementing green behavior in the workplace can lead to reactions in the company, including emotional feelings during interpersonal communication (Li et al., 2023). Early academics used self-determination theory to anticipate EGB (Mamun, 2023; Saini et al., 2025). Chinese research on self-determination theory is primarily based on narratives, with little pragmatic data (Yu et al. 2018). This study greatly advances practical application of self-determination theory in China. This study suggests that EWB improves employee self-esteem. This result broadens scope of study on EGB and the elements that influence self-esteem. This study found that utilizing OC and EE increases the link between EWB, EGB, and self-esteem, as well as the intermediate mechanism that connects EWB to EGB through self-esteem. The research on EWB's impact on self-esteem revealed that employees with a stronger sense of purpose are more likely to benefit from organizational commitments and employee involvement. Employees with a robust sense of purpose in organizational commitments and engagements tend to have greater self-esteem levels. This conclusion broadens research on pro-social behavior and EGB.

4.2 Practical Implications

Improving self-esteem and employee well-being, companies and individuals should promote employee green behavior. To improve employee green behaviour (EGB), companies could encourage employee well-being and self-esteem (Wang et al., 2024). To encourage green behavior and increase employee well-being, businesses should consider their green values when hiring and provide green training and learning opportunities. Under EGB, businesses place a greater focus on employee self-esteem. Using specialized approaches to identify employees with greater self-esteem levels can improve their well-being throughout job duties. Employees may improve their well-being by recognizing the significance of green behavior for society and business. This can boost self-esteem and encourage adoption of green practices. Initiatives can encourage good employee green behavior to demonstrate concern for the business and build a sense of support (Usman et al., 2024). This will make

staff feel valued by their managers for adopting environmentally friendly practices. Promoting employee well-being increases their overall environmentally conscious conduct.

4.3 Limitations and Future Research

Latest research expanded on previous studies by includes work-related inventive activity. The scale shows that EWB has an indirect impact on EGB, but self-esteem effectively mediates the relationship. This study offers additional research to assess its feasibility and its use in other areas of the service industry. Further research should incorporate more individual and organizational characteristics to better represent this study's findings.

4.4 Conclusion

The study examined the impact of EWB on EGB faculty members' eco-related knowledge. The researchers discovered that self-esteem completely controls association among green activities and well-being. This project augments EGB structures and develops knowledge of the advantages of green behavior among businesses and employees. The study promotes EWB and encourages employees to implement green workplace practices and prioritize the organization's sustainability. To boost employee green behaviour and self-esteem, top-level executives should promote an environmentally friendly workplace culture and give constructive feedback. The study found that EWB is a major predictor of EGB, with self-esteem serving as a mediator, organizational commitment and employee engagement as moderators. Employee involvement strengthens connection among EWB, EGB, and self-esteem, as well as method by which EWB impacts EGB. This study improves the measuring methodology and outcome variables for EGB, allowing businesses and workers to better understand the advantages of green behavior for those who engage in it. According to research, fostering EGB may motivate employees to adopt green practices, so contributing to the organization's sustainability. Policymakers can encourage green behaviour in the workplace and offer positive feedback to promote employee self-esteem and well-being. Employee green behaviour is critical in pushing businesses, particularly higher education institutions, to embrace sustainable practices.

Higher education institutions function as knowledge incubators for society and the economy. Lecturers in higher education institutions can contribute to environmental sustainability by safeguarding the bionetwork. This study intends to educate businesses on the benefits of employee green behaviour and the significance of encouraging environmentally friendly behavior in the organization.

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